

New Gravity Field Equation is derived by Einstein Field Equation in General Relativity Theory

Sangwha-Yi*

Department of Math, Taejon University 300-716, South Korea

*Corresponding Author: Sangwha-Yi, Department of Math, Taejon University 300-716, South Korea

Abstract: We found the 4-order curvature term satisfied the co-variant derivative. Einstein gravity field equation is consist of 2-order curvature terms. Hence, the 4-order curvature term and 2-order curvature terms make new gravity field equation. In this point, Einstein's gravity field equation can be modified by new 4-order curvature term because gravity field equation's term doesn't have to be 2-order term. Indeed, Einstein himself was like that, 0-order term, the cosmological term. Therefore, our theory is based on legitimate facts.

Keywords: 4-order curvature term; New gravity field equation; Einstein's 2-order terms;

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1. INTRODUCTION

We found the 4-order curvature term satisfied the co-variant derivative. Einstein gravity field equation is consist of 2-order curvature terms. Hence, the 4-order curvature term and 2-order curvature terms make new gravity field equation. In this point, Einstein's gravity field equation can be modified by new 4-order curvature term because gravity field equation's term doesn't have to be 2-order term. Indeed, Einstein himself was like that, 0-order term, the cosmological term. Therefore, our theory is based on legitimate facts. If energy-momentum tensor is zero, Einstein gravity field equation is

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R = 0 \quad (1)$$

Or if energy-momentum tensor is zero, the equation is add the cosmological term (0-order term)

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R + \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} = 0 \quad (2)$$

2. DERIVED 4-ORDER CURVATURE TERM AND NEW GRAVITY FIELD EQUATION

Einstein gravity field equation is satisfied by co-variant derivative.

$$(R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R)_{;\rho} = 0 \quad (3)$$

If energy-momentum tensor is zero, Einstein's 2-order contra-variant gravitational equation is

$$R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\nu} R = 0 \quad (4)$$

Also, if we deal with the co-variant derivative of 2-order contra-variant gravitational equation, we get

$$(R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g^{\mu\nu} R)_{;\rho} = 0 \quad (5)$$

If Eq(1) multiply Eq(4), then

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R)(R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g^{\mu\nu}R) \\
 &= R_{\mu\nu}R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g^{\mu\nu}R_{\mu\nu}R - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R^{\mu\nu}R + \frac{1}{4}g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu}R^2, \quad g^{\mu\nu}R_{\mu\nu} = R, g_{\mu\nu}R^{\mu\nu} = R, g_{\mu\nu}g^{\mu\nu} = 4 \\
 &= R_{\mu\nu}R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}R^2 - \frac{1}{2}R^2 + R^2 = R_{\mu\nu}R^{\mu\nu} \tag{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

New 4-order curvature term's co-variant derivative is

$$\begin{aligned}
 & (R_{\mu\nu}R^{\mu\nu})_{;\rho} = R_{\mu\nu;\rho}R^{\mu\nu} + R_{\mu\nu}R^{\mu\nu}_{;\rho} \\
 &= \{(R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R)(R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g^{\mu\nu}R)\}_{;\rho} \\
 &= (R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R)_{;\rho}(R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g^{\mu\nu}R) + (R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R)(R^{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g^{\mu\nu}R)_{;\rho} = 0 \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, new gravity field equation is consist of 2-order curvature terms and new 4-order curvature term.

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R + \Lambda'g_{\mu\nu}R_{\rho\sigma}R^{\rho\sigma} = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu} \tag{8}$$

Or new gravity field equation is consist of 0-order term (cosmological term) and 2-order terms and 4-order term

$$\Lambda g_{\mu\nu} + R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}g_{\mu\nu}R + \Lambda'g_{\mu\nu}R_{\rho\sigma}R^{\rho\sigma} = -\frac{8\pi G}{c^4}T_{\mu\nu} \tag{9}$$

3. CONCLUSION

We found the 4-order curvature term and new gravity field equation satisfied the co-variant derivative.

In new gravity field equation, Schwarzschild solution and Kerr solution do not change.

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